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Abstract:

Tribal Entrepreneurship as a concept is associated with the entrepreneurial activity of an individual belonging to tribal community in India. This community widely called Scheduled Tribe (ST) gets its legitimacy in Constitution of India under article 366 (26) that defines scheduled tribes and article 342 that prescribes procedure to specify ST. The essential characteristics of these community are *Primitive Traits, Geographical isolation, Distinct culture, Shy of contact with community at large, Economically backwardness*. Therefore, such studies are required to investigate into and understand the ethnographic variation to existing body of knowledge on Entrepreneurship. These studies have potential to serve as the inputs for government interventions in this domain as well as guiding pathway to potential and real tribal entrepreneurs.

This case study is based on the interviews of Tribal Entrepreneurs in the region of Dadra and Nagar Haveli (DNH). It is the district of Union Territory of Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Daman and Diu, India. This district has more than 50% of its population as ST. The case study unleashes empirical insights on some key aspects of Tribal Entrepreneurship such as, motivation, challenges, role of education and skill development, role of government, and its future in the region.

Keywords: Tribal, Entrepreneurship, Tribal Entrepreneurship, Tribal Entrepreneur.

1. Introduction:

Entrepreneurship is important for economic development. Entrepreneurs channelise the ideas and resources for meaningful offerings to the society. This offering they make earns economic benefits to all the stakeholders of the society. Thus, it brings the economic prosperity not just to themselves, but to its customers, the government, and human as well as natural society. Therefore, it makes sense to study this phenomenon with 360-degree perspective.

There is ample of literature available on various connotation to 'Entrepreneurship' and its types. However, Tribal Entrepreneurship is not much explored concept. This concept further requires the spatial understanding given the diversity among the tribal groups within various parts of India. Therefore, this study is one such effort to understand the entrepreneurship phenomena in the district of Dadra and Nagar Haveli, of Union Territory of Dadra and Nagar Haveli and Daman and Diu (UT of DNH & DD), India.

To keep it simple, '**Tribal Entrepreneurship**' herein is referred to '**the entrepreneurial activity taken up by a Tribal Entrepreneur**'. Tribal Entrepreneur is an entrepreneur who belongs to tribal community in India and statutorily know as an individual belonging to Scheduled Tribe (ST). Therefore, **Tribal entrepreneurship refers to the engagement of indigenous or tribal communities in various economic activities, including small businesses, start-ups, and enterprises**. India is home to a significant tribal population, and understanding the nuances of tribal entrepreneurship is crucial for promoting inclusive and sustainable economic development in various regions of the country.

Tribal Entrepreneurship needs to be studied for three main reasons that are associated with the entrepreneurs of tribal community: i) distinctive ethnic background, ii) lesser participation in economic development, and iii) lower socio-economic status.

2. Literature Review:

The existing studies on subject matter have explored following aspects:

Socio-economic and Cultural Context: Several studies have explored the socio-economic and cultural factors that influence tribal entrepreneurship in India. Traditional tribal practices, customs, and beliefs often shape their entrepreneurial ventures. Researchers have identified how cultural preservation and adherence to traditional values play a role in business decisions and practices among tribal entrepreneurs.

Barriers and Challenges: Tribal entrepreneurs face unique challenges that hinder their business growth and sustainability. Literature highlights obstacles such as limited access to formal education, financial resources, markets, and infrastructure. Additionally, land rights, bureaucratic hurdles, and lack of awareness about government schemes often act as barriers for tribal entrepreneurs.

Indigenous Knowledge and Innovation: Tribal communities possess valuable indigenous knowledge and skills that can be harnessed for entrepreneurship. Studies have explored how traditional knowledge and craftsmanship can be integrated into modern business practices, leading to the creation of unique products and services.

Government Policies and Interventions: Researchers have examined the role of government policies and interventions in promoting tribal entrepreneurship. Some studies assess the effectiveness of various schemes, subsidies, and development programs aimed at supporting tribal entrepreneurs and uplifting their communities.

Success Stories and Best Practices: Several case studies highlight successful tribal entrepreneurial ventures in India. Understanding these success stories helps identify best practices and strategies that can be replicated or adapted to other tribal communities. Additionally, these case studies shed light on how tribal entrepreneurs overcome challenges and build sustainable businesses.

Social Impact and Sustainability: The social impact of tribal entrepreneurship is a crucial aspect of research. Scholars have analysed how these ventures contribute to poverty alleviation, community development, and women's empowerment within tribal societies. Moreover, there is a focus on the environmental sustainability practices adopted by tribal entrepreneurs.

Thus, Tribal entrepreneurship in India presents both challenges and opportunities. While there are barriers to overcome, the rich cultural heritage and indigenous knowledge of these communities offer unique prospects for sustainable and inclusive economic development. The literature reviewed suggests that a holistic approach, considering cultural preservation, access to resources, and government support, is essential for fostering successful tribal entrepreneurship in India. Policymakers and researchers need to collaborate to design and implement effective strategies to promote and support tribal entrepreneurship while preserving their cultural identity and heritage.

3. Methodology:

This study is based on case study research method, it is a type under qualitative research approach that involves in-depth investigation and analysis of a specific individual, group, organization, event, or phenomenon. It aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of the case's context, dynamics, and underlying processes. Case research methodology is commonly used in various fields, including social sciences, business, psychology, education, and healthcare, among others. This study being inter-disciplinary (i.e. social sciences, and business), researchers deploy case research method.

This case study aims to understand following set of research questions:

1. What is the motivation and challenges faced by Tribal Entrepreneurs?
2. Does education and skill development play a role in Tribal Entrepreneurship?
3. What contribution do Tribal Entrepreneurship make to the tribal community and the society at large in DNH?
4. What is the future of Tribal Entrepreneurship in the region of DNH?

To address these questions interviews were conducted with the Tribal Entrepreneurs at DNH. Also, relevant document and records were accessed and in some instances the observations were recorded. Thus, these insights are proposed for contributing to the existing literature on entrepreneurship.

4. Discussion:

Based on interviews the empirical insights are presented as follows under the headings as: Motivation for Entrepreneurship, Challenges faced by Tribal Entrepreneurs, Role of education and skill development in Tribal Entrepreneurship, Government support and improvement needed for encouragement of Tribal Entrepreneurship, Contribution to the society, and future of Tribal Entrepreneurship in the region of DNH.

4.1. Motivation for Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurs involved in cultural and traditional knowledge-based enterprise are motivated by their parents and society. They get interested to take up these activities at large scale and try to capitalize as a source of income. These entrepreneurs are also concerned about the social and environmental effects and thus try to leverage their activities to the social and environmental benefits. For instance, one of the respondents to this case study is into enterprising activity of 'Varli Painting'. He shares that, he got interested in varli painting while his school days watching one of his teachers drawing varli painting on the school walls. Later he took formal education in art and painting and self-taught the varli painting. Today, Varli Painting and his work has brought him a lot of attention. He trains the kids nearby his house and remunerates them for the work done by them. Another such Tribal Entrepreneur in the region is engaged in honey and organic farming. He got influenced by his father. This well-informed entrepreneur is concerned of environment and takes every effort to conserve and enrich it. He shared that while honey farming at his farm sites the honeybees act as a good source of pollination in surrounding areas that further helps the trees and plants with higher productivity and fertility.

The Tribal Entrepreneurs indulged in contemporary entrepreneurial activities credit the interest in their respective field or work to be the source of motivation. For them it is only the interest driven by dedication that leads to an entrepreneurial venture. For instance, a respondent to this case who is involved in "Securities Trading", shared that it was his interest in stock markets that kept him going in the hard early days to see himself as an established entrepreneur in the region.

4.2 Challenges faced by Tribal Entrepreneurs: as enumerated below with brief discussion the challenges are as follows:

- **Funds Constraint:** generally due to low socio-economic background Tribal Entrepreneurs always have funds constraints. The entrepreneurs say that due to fund constraints many a times they are not able to turn their ideas into commercial enterprise. They also shared that fund constraints makes it difficult to run day to day operation in an early stage and hinders the growth.
- **Issues in Form of Business:** entrepreneurs face difficulty in continuity of the business in case of partnerships. They find partnership as a most viable form of business to deal various challenges but are unable to continue with the same due to differences and interest conflicts.
- **No planning for revenue generation:** even though the entrepreneurs are successful in establishing an enterprise, they face a challenge of consistency in operational revenues. It is largely a challenge for cultural and traditional knowledge-based enterprises.
- **Ignorance of marketing and its significance:** few entrepreneurs are aware of the marketing and its significance for the success of an enterprise. The entrepreneurs aware of marketing aspect have been associated with the government initiative such as 'TRIFED'¹. However, it is observed that they are largely dependent on it and show lesser or no efforts for marketing their products and services.
- **Inability to reach the government support:** the entrepreneurs were aware of few initiatives and agreed on participation in it at some extent. But they are dissatisfied with the support extended stating that these initiatives should provide consistent support at least at early stage of startup and see if the support or benefits are really reaching to a Tribal Entrepreneur. They also complained of unawareness on many such governments schemes and policies and lamented on administrative setup of not communicating the same to them.
- **Lack of managerial skills:** like accounting and costing, managing resources and men, supply chain etc. It is a huge challenge as it is a costly affair to outsource or hire human resource for these skills.
- **Weak networking:** entrepreneurs have agreed on the fact that they need to improve their networking. They also say that its difficult for them to create good networks not just out of their community but also within the community.

¹ TRIFED – Tribal Cooperative Marketing Development Federation of India Ltd., initiative of Ministry of Tribal Affairs, Government of India.

Fig. A: Challenges faced by Tribal Entrepreneurs in DNH

Source: Self-drafted based on primary data collected for this study.

4.3 Role of education and skill development in Tribal Entrepreneurship: Education helps in many ways in every walk of life and so in the Tribal Entrepreneurship as well. Tribal Entrepreneurs in the region say that elementary education helps to acquire requisite knowledge for running the enterprise. For example, plethora of knowledge and skillset can be learnt via internet and YouTube if one has elementary education. Thus, following below are some pointers enumerating the role of education and skill development in Tribal Entrepreneurship:

- An educated entrepreneur can harness the technology advancements happening rapidly in the world and equip the enterprise accordingly.
- Education also forms a key to better communication that is vital to run an enterprise.
- Entrepreneurs believe that education also imparts courage and confidence to lead an entrepreneurial venture.
- Education further aid to quick decision making.
- Well educated entrepreneur always has an alternative in case of adverse situation in the entrepreneurship. One always has the flexibility to switch between entrepreneurship and job opportunities.

However, education should not be directly associated with entrepreneurial success. It should develop and individual to be humble enough to accept the realities of life and business. One should not shy away from humble startup initiatives and work tenaciously for its success. Entrepreneurial success demands self-motivation and dedication along with education.

4.4 Government Support and Improvement needed for encouragement of Tribal Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurs agree on the essentiality of government support through policies and interventions as and when required. However, they have expressed improvement in the role of government for promoting the Tribal Entrepreneurship in the region. Following below are few areas of concern entrepreneurs expressed:

- **Low / No awareness of the government schemes and policies:** entrepreneurs are mostly unaware of such schemes or policies. The entrepreneurs interviewed for this study were aware of two government initiatives i.e. TRIFED and SC, ST, OBC, and Minorities Financial support. They also said that they were not well informed about the schemes and thus hesitate to approach for the same. Thus, local bodies need to be widely involved in spreading the awareness. For instance, at the village level Sarpanch should be notified of such government initiative and should be directed to discuss them in the Gram Sabha (Panchayat level meetings).
- **Training to be provided in local language/dialect:** Language is a major barrier whenever the government organizes trainings in the region. Thus, if these training could be imparted in local language/dialect will prove of good support.
- **Government support up-till startup attains breakeven point:** Entrepreneurs are in a view that government support should be consistent till a startup attains breakeven point. The entrepreneurs with traditional entrepreneurial activities (i.e. Horticulture, Agrobased, Varli Painting, etc.) are approached by the nodal officers or government representatives only for specific events or launch

of some scheme and later left on their own. Thus, such acts of government representatives can discourage the budding Tribal Entrepreneurs.

- **Pilferage of benefits from government:** in different ways is experienced by the entrepreneurs mostly traditional entrepreneurial activities. For instance, at the events may it be state, national, or international level many a times government representatives, represent the tribal entrepreneur. An entrepreneur shared that he was called for some training as a resource person and was promised a remuneration that he never got. Also, an instance was shared that involved monetary aid being given to an entrepreneur had pilferage. Therefore, this is an area of concern.
- **Red Tapism:** bureaucracy is largely blamed for this. Entrepreneurs have faced it in terms of delay in work, difficulty to reach officers, people with connects getting easy access, etc.

Government schemes and policies should be assessed by the administration and see if these areas of improvement do exist in the region. If so, it would require an attention for encouragement of Tribal Entrepreneurship.

4.5 Contribution to the society: Tribal Entrepreneurship certainly has many benefits for tribal society, but these can be extended to the larger society at large. Some of the ways it can be done are i) employment generation locally as well as encourage others in society to take up an entrepreneurship, ii) development of peripheral areas by various income generation avenues because of comparatively larger entrepreneurial initiatives, iii) boost the economic activity locally can help in attacking on poverty and alleviate the society.

4.6 Future of Tribal Entrepreneurship in DNH:adequate education and training can provide further impetus to success of Tribal Entrepreneurship in the region. Also, following aspects indicate better future prospect of Tribal Entrepreneurship in the region.

- **Emerging Second Generation Tribal Entrepreneurs:** gradually the existing tribal enterprises are entering into phase second generation. Second generation entrepreneurs with better education and skills will surely take enterprises to new heights.
- **Tribal Youth attracted to entrepreneurship:** wider youth section looks up to entrepreneurial venture over the jobs. Youth of this generation desires for quick growth and development. Thus, it will push Tribal Entrepreneurship in the region.
- **Government Initiatives:**at national level and regional level initiatives specially targeting this section of entrepreneurs will boost Tribal Entrepreneurship in the region.

5. Conclusion:

Entrepreneurs involved in cultural and traditional knowledge-based enterprise are motivated by their parents and society. Whereas the Tribal Entrepreneurs indulged in contemporary entrepreneurial activities credit the interest in their respective field or work to be the source of motivation. The challenges faced by them are ***fund constraints, issues in form of business, no planning for revenue generation, ignorance of marketing and its significance, inability to reach the government support, lack of managerial skills, weak networking.*** The entrepreneurs credit education and skill development, and governmental support for their success. However, they raised the concerns regarding government support such as ***low / no awareness of the government schemes and policies, training should be provided in local language/dialect, government support up-till startup attains breakeven point, Pilferage of benefits from government, and red tapism.***

Tribal Entrepreneurship has potential not just to contribute to tribal society by the entire society. The contribution is in terms of employment generation, development of local areas and tackling of poverty and alleviating the living standards. In region of DNH, the future appears favourable considering the indicators like, ***emerging second generation tribal entrepreneurs, tribal youth attracted to entrepreneurship, government initiatives.***

6. Teaching Notes:

6.1 Objectives of the Case:

- To enlighten the readers / participants with the essence of ‘Tribal Entrepreneurship’ while gathering empirical insights from the case of UT of DNH.

- To get readers / participants identify the challenges faced by tribal entrepreneurs in the region.
- To enable readers / participants to assess the extent of government support for Tribal Entrepreneurship with special reference to the region of DNH.
- To make readers / participants understand & contribute the thoughts on the future prospect of Tribal Entrepreneurship in the region of DNH.

6.2 Level of Analysis: This case can be adopted to understand the types of entrepreneurs forming part of studies at undergraduate and graduate level programmes within social sciences domain. The case may be used by various nodal agencies of government conducting programs, and trainings on entrepreneurship, skill development, standup India, etc. Also, statutory bodies such as MSME, ICAI, ICSI may adopt this case in their respective programs and seminars on entrepreneurship.

6.3 Broad Discussion Questions: Based on the case study following below are the broad questions:

1. What is the motivation and challenges faced by Tribal Entrepreneurs? Compare it with Non-Tribal Entrepreneurs.
2. How can education and skill development play a role in Tribal Entrepreneurship?
3. What contribution can Tribal Entrepreneurship make to the tribal community and the society at large?
4. What is the future of Tribal Entrepreneurship?

6.4 Potential Analysis: This case study analysis for a pure academic purpose can have four sections.

- **Section 1: Introduction to the Tribal Entrepreneurship** - (*Key points of discourse can be, i.) entrepreneurship and its types, ii.) essence of tribal entrepreneurship, iii.) comparison entrepreneurship vs. tribal entrepreneurship*)
- **Section 2: Problem Statement** – (*To be defined based on the stand/viewpoint of case participant. For example, if a participant is using this case as a comparison to some another tribal region, she can coin a problem statement as ‘need to compare tribal entrepreneurship within two different regions.’*)
- **Section 3: Addressing the Broad Discussion Questions** – (*The question should be supported by established academic text along with insights from this case and such others. Illustration should be included.*)
- **Section 4: Case Decision Making** – (*Considering the defined problem statement potential solution, suggestion, and recommendation need to be given to the stakeholders identified in case discourse*)

6.5 Potential benefit of the case: perhaps for *academia and social-sciences students* studying subject of Entrepreneurship. They can be educated with a type of entrepreneurship, its challenges, role of government and prospects. **Government** can test back the empirical evidence discussed in the case and design the plan of action accordingly for encouraging entrepreneurship. **General society and youth** reading this case can use these insights to understand the ground reality of entrepreneurship and spread awareness as well as get motivated to be the job creators.

6.6 Session Plan to Support Academics:

	Off-Class	In-Class
Pre-discussion	Assign the case well in advance to class for discussion. (<i>A week before is desirable</i>) List of pre-reading and resources need to be made available to case participants.	Announce the case and expectations in advance. State the defined levels of cognitive abilities as per blooms taxonomy to be assessed through the case analysis.
In-discussion	Participant needs to decide in off-class what shall be her position in a case and while discussion. Participant needs to prepare a draft	Case Moderator shall give an opening remark and direct the discussion by probing the questions if required. Participants shall enter in discussion

	Off-Class	In-Class
	of case resolution.	and articulate their position taken in advance if required based on ongoing case discussion. Case Moderator to consolidate the relevant case discussion points. (2 Hours of Case Discussion)
Post-discussion	Participant to prepare a learning note based on class discussion and revisit their draft of case resolution. (Give atleast 2 days time)	Case Moderator to reinforce the case discourse with theory of the topic based on the consolidated points taken in case discussion. (1 Hour)

If the case is considered for assessment & evaluation the evaluator should be invited for a case discussion in classroom. And if the case is given as part of the written examinations scheme of marking should be designed as per the case analysis discussed above to this teaching notes. Maximum marks allotted should be 25.

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